

D6.7 Report on the results of dissemination activities (2)

WP6 Enabling environment and awareness raising

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Executive summary

The key for a successful dissemination and communication strategy during the all live of the project has been the application of a common framework, providing the consortium with a common process and a set of common criteria, with the purpose to identify, monitor and select the suited dissemination channels.

Another important parameter for the efficient dissemination plan has been the direct involvement of all partners of the consortium in the process, especially those responsible for pilot implementation. All project partners have developed a sense of co-ownership of the project as they have been involved at all stages of the strategy's development. Each consortium member has responsibility for a particular aspect of the strategy's implementation, but also a shared vision and common understanding of where content was the key to target the right audience.

All dissemination activities have been in line with the protection of IPR as well as the confidentiality obligations, which were established in the Consortium Agreement (CA).

DIANA guarantees that it has adopted the technical and organizational nature appropriate security in accordance with the provisions of "REGULATION (EU) 2016/679 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT and OF THE COUNCIL on April 27 of 2016 relating to the protection of the physical persons regarding personal data processing and the free circulation of these data, with entrance in force the day May 25 of 2018, from now on, GDPR".

The structure of the document is to provide an overview of dissemination and communication activities carried out by the DIANA consortium. The previous dissemination report, D6.6 Report on the results of Dissemination activities highlighted the multi-channel strategy agreed upon by members of the Consortium with regards to raising awareness of the project.

Dissemination activities have been a horizontal activity within DIANA project, and have been strongly related to all the other work packages. DIANA aims, plans and (interim) results have been disseminated and communicated to all interested audiences from the project kick-off onwards through a large set of different dissemination channels. The main assets disseminated are the DIANA activities, data products and services; the DIANA service platform and its components including the web and mobile applications; novel knowledge generated through the implementation of the project; and the data collected during the pilot implementation.

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It is the aim of this final Report on results of dissemination activities to present both the most recent reporting period but also the success of dissemination across the whole life span of the project. Therefore, this report offers a review of the previous two reporting periods and concludes with the most recent one.

First period establishing DIANA visual identity was a major achievement in the first reporting period (M1-M12), aiming to set the baseline for a brand identity for the commercial service. Along with the development of the project's official website and the activation of its official Twitter, Facebook, and LinkedIn accounts, which provide platforms for communicating news and material related to DIANA to specific audiences (e.g. younger, technologically-aware farmers on Facebook), and for sharing the latest information on the DIANA services. The first year also marked the production of the first Pilot area videos with interviews to users on DIANA Youtube channel. Some local press articles drew attention to the project and sites. The first report on dissemination revealed the partners' unanimous commitment to making the project known both regionally and internationally. During the first period, the project's newsletters, provided information, results and events related to the project. Several experts were contacted to take part in the project Advisory Board. Specific dissemination material were created and distributed at external conferences (i.e. audience-focused presentations);

Second period The second reporting period (M13-M24) continued in the same direction for dissemination, and revolved around employing the established strategy in order to draw attention to the newly operational DIANA sites. In order to keep target groups informed of the project, many dissemination activities in various parts of Europe, as well as maintain an awareness of potential new dissemination opportunities, the second newsletter was published in 2018, to be circulated. An important milestone for dissemination in the second period was the preparation of a project-wide press release announcing the start of the services, to be disseminated through official EC channels. Sites also raised awareness by organising Regional Meetings with stakeholders once the platform and services became operational. The DIANA consortium partners have been active in 25 events in various modalities: oral or poster presentations, keynotes, panel members, exhibitors, and networking participants. D6.6 provides a list of the corresponding activities, which at the end of year 2 already exceed the initial target values.

Third period The third and final reporting period of the project (M25-M36), which is the main focus of the present report, gradually oriented the established dissemination strategy towards the announcement of the project's final results. The second half of 2019 was particularly marked by taking concrete steps in the organisation of the DIANA Final Review Meeting and DIANA Final Event: Monitoring Water Abstractions with Copernicus (Success Stories from the H2020 project DIANA), which took place at Zaragoza EIP Water Innovation Conference. The rich harvest from 3 project years was presented, with emphasis on success stories from the DIANA pilot cases as well as the relevance for the WFD (Water Framework Directive).

In terms of event participation, DIANA partners have continued throughout the entire year to participate in national and international conferences, tallying 9 Conference - Oral presentations in 2019 with a participation in 14 National and International events and 19 Stakeholder engagement events and presentations. An open workshop dedicated to DIANA to bring attention to the most recent results of the project and one Workshop on EO downstream Services in Horizon Europe to gather feedback and recommendations from the H2020 EO downstream projects to feed into the wider stakeholder consultation process led by DG GROW for the preparation of the Horizon Europe space programme. 8 scientific papers have been published and uploaded on DIANA website.

DIANA project results have also been advertised on Tools for Dissemination & Exploitation for H2020 results (Horizon Results Platform).

The important task of promotional video production was taken up. It has been uploaded for dissemination on DIANA YouTube channel and DIANA web.

The dissemination and communication material and activities that have been produced or undertaken during the project include:

- the visual identity of the project, established at the beginning of the project, aiming to set the baseline for a brand identity for the commercial service;
- a public website launched in M05 and regularly updated, to serve as a single source of information concerning the project results and activities, and to disseminate news;
- the DIANA page on Facebook, the LinkedIn group and the DIANA Twitter account, which provide platforms for communicating news and material related to DIANA to specific audiences (e.g. younger, technologically-aware farmers on Facebook), and for sharing the latest information on the DIANA services;
- 13 videos on DIANA YouTube channel (general, pilot areas, training);

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- project newsletters, providing information, results and events related to the project;
- specific dissemination materials used and distributed at external conferences (i.e. audience-focused presentations);
- representation in conferences and media as well as the publication of scientific papers, enhancing DIANA's visibility and enabling the development of a solid network amongst agricultural and Earth Observation (EO) academic and industrial stakeholders at both European and regional level;
- the Final Event held in the context of the EIP-Water Innovation Conference in Zaragoza.

All consortium partners took part in the respective dissemination activities and contributed to achieving maximum attention and awareness beyond the project consortium.

All dissemination and communication activities were planned to be enhanced and amplified in the last project year. With convincing outcomes of pilot deployment and co-evaluation in hand, the intention has been to create success stories in different media, tailored to the different target audiences.

1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose and scope

The key for a successful dissemination and communication strategy has been the application of a common framework, providing the consortium with a common process and a set of common criteria, with the purpose to identify, monitor and select the suited dissemination channels.

Another important parameter for the success of the dissemination plan is the direct involvement of all partners of the consortium in the process, especially those responsible for pilot implementation. All project partners have developed a sense of co-ownership of the project as they have been involved at all stages of the strategy's development. Each consortium member has responsibility for a particular aspect of the strategy's implementation, but also a shared vision and common understanding of what has to be disseminated together with a way of describing this to the audiences outside of the project that may benefit from the project work.

All dissemination activities have been in line with the protection of IPR as well as the confidentiality obligations, which were established in the Consortium Agreement (CA). All partners have actively engaged in the dissemination and stakeholder engagement activities conducted so far and are committed to continue along the lifespan of the project and beyond.

The purpose of this document is to provide an overview of dissemination and communication activities carried out by the DIANA consortium during the three years of the project.

All activities have followed the DIANA Dissemination and Communication Strategy laid out in D6.1 and D6.2, which is briefly recapitulated below.

Image: Horizont result platform

1.2. Key Elements of the DIANA Dissemination Strategy

The core objective of DIANA Dissemination and Communication Strategy (D6.1 and D6.2) is to provide a structure and roadmap for disseminating the concept, methodologies, pilots and outcomes of the project to particular audiences and to the wider public. In brief, the main objectives underpinning the DIANA strategy are to:

- Raise awareness and provide high visibility of the project and later on of the product, among the target groups;
- Establish a strong brand identity from the beginning;
- Encourage involvement of other stakeholders;
- Raise awareness of policy makers and public bodies;
- Facilitate synergies with similar or complementary initiatives and;
- Promote, implement and spread the use of the service.

The expected results of the dissemination and communication strategy are: raising awareness; identification of target groups and how they can exploit project results; and promotion of active participation in the project.

The following sections provide a brief recapitulation of the definitions in D6.1 and D6.2 (Dissemination and Communication Strategy (1) and (2)).

1.2.1 Main assets disseminated

- 💧 DIANA data products and services aimed at enabling water management authorities to systematically and efficiently detect and estimate the level of non-authorized water abstractions for irrigation, pro-actively plan for and manage their water resources in drought conditions as well as better implement the WFD;
- 💧 DIANA service platform and its components including the web and mobile applications, the GIS dashboard and the REST API to be employed by all DIANA applications and modules for information retrieval and storage;
- 💧 Novel knowledge to be generated through the implementation of the project with respect to the application of EO derived data and technologies for identifying and estimating the amounts of irrigation water abstracted without authorisation in different operational, administrative, cultural and legal contexts across the EU;
- 💧 Data to be collected and produced in the frame of DIANA activities (e.g. EO-based, satellite, meteorological and ancillary data as well as data derived from the identification of the user requirements, the co-creation workshops, the evaluation and validation activities, etc.).

1.2.2 Target groups and audiences

Identifying the target groups has enabled the consortium to decide where and how to market DIANA in an effective and less costly way. Furthermore, segmenting the market has helped in identifying the similarities between the different target groups, as well as their differences, in order to better understand them and make the service and/or product more appealing and interesting to them.

In the table below we present the different target groups of DIANA and we also include a wider audience segment to which the action itself and its results will be communicated:

Table 1. Different target groups of DIANA.

Target group	Activity of target group	Example
Water managers	Responsible for monitoring and inspecting abstractions of water for irrigation	Public authorities or associations of irrigators depending on national/regional particularities

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Authorities	Responsible for developing and implementing water/drought management plans and/or the WDF as well as issue irrigation water rights	River basin authorities, national, regional or local authorities
Farmers, agricultural cooperatives and consultancies	Active in the agricultural sector	Agribusiness professionals, advisors, innovation intermediaries
Research and Academia	Also with activities relevant to the agricultural sector	Academic institutions, non-university public research organisations, research and technology organisations
Non-governmental organisations and civic society groups	Interested in sustainable water management in the EU and aimed at addressing relevant social challenges and needs	Associations and NGOs
Other Stakeholders	That may be interested in project outcomes	Policy and decision makers at EU level, etc
Wider public	People that have an interest on the issue	People that have an interest on the issue

2. Dissemination channels and results

This section provides a brief recapitulation of the dissemination materials and channels, as well as a summary of results. All details can be found in D6.2 (Dissemination and Communication Plan (2)), D6.3 (Promotional material), D6.4 (Social media accounts), and D6.5 (DIANA Web Portal). The emphasis is here on the results achieved.

2.1. Visual identity

An integrated and coherent visual identity underpins all communication products and tools and forms the basis for a commercial brand. The visual identity consists of the logo, colour pallet, and additional visual elements (e.g. the blue header bar used in templates) which work together to form a coherent and easily-recognisable whole.

By creating a comprehensive and clean logo, and investing in high-quality design, the WP6 team aimed to maximize and prolong the attention and interest of target audiences and convey the impression of a professional and operational undertaking, as opposed to a research project or a concept under development. In order to become widely recognizable as a brand with as much recognition and awareness as possible throughout the three years of the project.

As required by Horizon 2020 rules on dissemination (European Commission, 2012), across all the outputs of the DIANA project, and accompanying the logo, text concerning the source of the project's funding and disclosing the Grant Agreement number is provided, along with the European flag: *"This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 730109"*.

The logo (see Figure 1) was created very early in the project, together with the associated colour palette. Based on these elements, the strong and coherent visual identity was also expressed in a series of templates, applied to the various project related documents: Deliverable documents; Non-Deliverable Documents (such as memos, notes or letters); Deliverable document internal reviews; Event reports; Press releases; Presentations; Project Info Fact-Sheet; Project Poster; Project Brochure; Project Leaflet.

Figure 1: DIANA logo

This strong DIANA project visual identity is expected to also enhance and assist all exploitation and commercialisation actions (performed or planned) within WP5, towards the successful commercial exploitation of the project outputs (products and services) and the creation of a DIANA branding during and beyond the lifespan of the project, in accordance with the DIANA exploitation and commercialisation plan and related activities.

2.2. Website

The DIANA website (<http://diana-h2020.eu/>) was released in M04 (as described in detail in the deliverable D6.5 DIANA Web Portal) and represents a central point of dissemination for all target audiences. At this stage, the website contains information about the project (structure, objectives, concept, team, etc.) and can be used as a communication tool that assists partners in reaching stakeholders, as well as the wider audience. The project website has been further populated during the 2nd year of the project, and has been updated in the third year focusing on improving and expanding the general information already provided with additional content (news, activities, events, etc.). The aim is to deliver content that attracts and raises the number of unique and returning visitors.

The website statistics, according to Google analytics, show a number of over 3000 visitors at the end of year 1 and over 13.000 visitors at the end of year 3.

2.3. E-mail list and Newsletter

DIANA mailing list is continuously populated with new contacts and members, both from the website subscription button (self-registered subscriptions) but also from the consortium continuous engagement and networking activities. DIANA project updates and an electronic copy of the DIANA newsletter are being circulated to the mailing list in order to maintain members' interest, increase engagement with the DIANA expanding community and leverage word-of-mouth communication about DIANA services.

During the 3rd year of the project a number of upscaling-actions have been executed, including the launch of the third DIANA newsletter, intensive networking activities, and expanding the DIANA email list of 240 members.

2.4. DIANA on Social Media

DIANA project has established a coherent social media presence, as described in detail in the deliverable D6.4 Social Media Accounts (M05). Active project accounts have been established in Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube, engaging and interacting with followers.

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Using social networks allows the DIANA project not only to reach and communicate with a large group of people nearly instantly, but also to disseminate value generated to the wide public.

Based on the consortium experience gained during the 1st and 2nd year of the project, and in parallel to the continuous evaluation of the impact and reach generated through the different social media, the consortium decided to further customise them and assign specific project material to be circulated through each social media account.

Thus the Facebook account is being used for “wide public” dissemination actions, Twitter for wide public dissemination and synergies with “water related” influencers (Twitter represents the most dynamic way of communicating and cross-posting relevant news that are either DIANA originals or relevant third party/other organisation posts, building in this way greater awareness), LinkedIn for “Experts and Scientific community” dissemination purposes and YouTube for disseminating video material to all audiences (a variation of video material will be provided to address the various audience target groups).

Table 2. Social media channels of DIANA project.

Social Media Channel	Main type of Material
Facebook	Engagement material, infographics, meeting pictures, practical abstracts etc.
Twitter	Relevant conferences and events material
LinkedIn	Public deliverables, scientific publications, White papers
YouTube	Videos

The DIANA Twitter account can be found [here](#) and followed using ‘@H2020_DIANA’.

The DIANA Facebook account can be found [here](#).

The DIANA LinkedIn Group Page can be found [here](#).

The DIANA YouTube channel can be found [here](#).

2.5. Dissemination Key Performance Indicators (KPI)

Table 3 shows the development of a number of Key Performance Indicators (KPI), as defined in D6.1. The expected target values have remained as initially defined.

Table 3. DIANA dissemination key performance indicators (KPI).

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Performance Indicator	Target Value	1 st year	2 nd	3 rd Year	Means of verification
Visitors to the project website	6.000	3.004	8000	14192	Google analytics
“Likes” on DIANA Facebook page	500	115	427	626*	Facebook account data
Followers of DIANA on Twitter	300	15	51	153	Twitter account data
Members on LinkedIn group	200	10	31	106	LinkedIn account data
Number of viewers of audiovisual material on YouTube	1000	n/a ⁹	149	809**	Number of views on YouTube
Publications on mass media	45	3	6	18	Dissemination reporting
Scientific publications	5	2	1	8	Dissemination reporting
Events to be attended by Project partners	10	9	12	22	Dissemination reporting
Newsletters produced	12	n/a	1	3	Copies available from reporting or via website
Number of subscribers to the newsletter	300	n/a	44	240	List of recipients
Number of contacts established in the NoI	200	17 mail lists	50	>200	List of stakeholders
Number of distributed printed material	2000	200	>1500	>3000	Dissemination reporting

**632 following ** 61 subscribers*

3. Dissemination activities and results

All planned actions for the first and second year of the project have been carried out successfully and according to the plan. All consortium partners took part in the respective dissemination activities and contributed to achieving maximum attention and awareness beyond the project consortium.

All project partners are in a strong position to develop an effective “personal” dissemination strategy, building on key existing channels. These channels and links will provide direct access to the target groups and will act as core channels that will support the project’s sustainability and its effective exit strategy.

In the following sections, we examine all relevant activities carried out during the first two years of the project.

DIANA project results have also been advertised on Tools for Dissemination & Exploitation for H2020 results (Horizon Results Platform) and CORDIS:

(<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/206073/factsheet/en>)

3.1. Network of Interest

The establishment and management of DIANA Network of Interest (NoI) has been and will be an ongoing activity during the entire life of the project, as well as after the end of the project. The main aim of establishing and expanding the “DIANA Network of Interest” is to have it act as a main dissemination pole for the engagement of DIANA target groups.

The DIANA NoI enables project partners to communicate the project objectives and disseminate its results on local, regional, national and European level. So far, the DIANA NoI counts 50 members. All NoI participants are encouraged to be involved in discussions concerning technical and scientific issues of the project through the official DIANA website, and they will be invited to participate in the project policy workshops.

Even though the effort is and will be to expand the NoI members list as a whole, special attention is given to attract those members that have the intention and the potential to utilise the DIANA solution and, above all, to its future customers’ base (those stakeholders who have the potential to purchase the solution).

3.2. Dissemination to scientific peers

This is the “classical” dissemination activities, essentially consisting of scientific publications in peer-reviewed journals and oral presentation at scientific conferences (sometimes including a proceedings article published in a conference volume and/or with ppt presentations available online). It addresses the “Research and Academia” target group.

The DIANA consortium has so far produced eleven scientific papers in peer-reviewed journals and reviewed conference proceedings, see Table 4 below. One article is now under submission.

The oral presentations at scientific conferences and trainings are listed in Annex A (a total of eight). The DIANA partners have either presented the project as a whole or specific actions and results (scientific knowledge and methodologies emerging).

Table 4. Scientific Publications (Open Access).

Publication	Participating Partner details
Negula, I. D.; Badea, A.; Moise, C.; Poenaru, V. (2017). "Earth observation satellite data in support of water management for agriculture", <i>AgroLife Scientific Journal</i> 2017 Vol.6 No.2 pp.133-136 ref.12. http://www.agrolifejournal.usamv.ro/pdf/vol.VI_2/Art19.pdf	ROSA
Alfonso Calera, Isidro Campos, Anna Osann, Guido D’Urso and Massimo Menti. “Remote Sensing for Crop Water Management: From ET Modelling to Services for the End Users”, <i>Sensors</i> 2017, 17(5), 1104 https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/17/5/1104 https://doi.org/10.3390/s17051104	AgriSat/UCLM, Ariospace
Poenaru, V., Badea, A., Cimpeanu, S., Irimescu, A. (2018). “Multi-temporal Sentinel 1 and Sentinel 2 time series analysis for the mapping of irrigated crops in the Great Island of Braila”, <i>Journal of Integrative Agricultures</i> , under review.	ROSA
"De Michele C., Falanga Bolognesi S., Belfiore O. R. Earth Observation Data To Detect Irrigated Areas: An Application In Southern Italy. The Ever Growing use of Copernicus across Europe's Regions: a selection of 99 stories by local and regional authorities, 11/2018: Chapter AGRICULTURE, FOOD, FORESTRY AND FISHERIES: pages 51; NEURES, European Space Agency and European Commission. (2018)" https://www.copernicus.eu/sites/default/files/2018-12/PUBLICATION_Copernicus4regions_2018.pdf	Ariospace

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<p>Falanga Bolognesi S., Belfiore O. R., De Michele, C., D'Urso, G. Monitoraggio operativo dell'irrigazione in regione Campania (Italia) mediante l'utilizzo del prodotto Harmonized Landsat Sentinel-2 (HLS). Atti della XXIII Conferenza Nazionale ASITA. 12-14 Novembre 2019. (2019) http://atti.asita.it/ASITA2019/Pdf/032.pdf</p>	Ariespace
<p>"D'Urso G., De Michele, C., Bolognesi, F. S., Belfiore, O. R. Operation monitoring of irrigation in the Campania Region (Italy) for the compliance of EU Water Directive by using Sentinel-2 data: the DIANA Project. Conference Proceeding: Living Planet Symposium - ESA. Milano, Italy, 13 – 17 May 2019 (2019)." https://lps19.esa.int/NikalWebsitePortal/living-planet-symposium-</p>	Ariespace
<p>Falanga Bolognesi S., Belfiore O. R., De Michele C., Mastracchio C., Ferraiuolo A., Natalizio M., D'Urso G. Controllo delle aree irrigate nei Consorzi di Bonifica mediante analisi multi-temporale di dati Sentinel-2. Atti della XXI Conferenza Nazionale ASITA. 2017. (2017) http://atti.asita.it/ASITA2017/Pdf/146.pdf</p>	Ariespace
<p>Falanga Bolognesi S., Belfiore O. R., De Michele C., Mula I., D'Urso G. Stima dei fabbisogni irrigui in Regione Campania da dati di OT mediante metodologia IRRISAT. Atti della XXI Conferenza Nazionale ASITA. 2017. (2017) http://atti.asita.it/ASITA2017/Pdf/156.pdf</p>	Ariespace
<p>De Michele, C., Natalizio, M., & D'Urso, G. (2017). Applying earth observation to detect non-authorized irrigation: the case study of Consorzio Sannio Alifano (Italy). <i>Agriculture & Forestry/Poljoprivreda i Sumarstvo</i>, 63(1); DOI: 10.17707/AgricultForest.63.1.01</p>	Ariespace/Sannio Alifano
<p>Osann, A., Calera, A., Garrido-Rubio, J., Calera, M., López-González, M.LL., Olivas, P. National agricultural journal "Tierras". (2019) DIANA Project: Detection of irrigated surfaces and estimation of water consumption through time series of images" https://diana-h2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019_06_Tierras-Proyecto-DIANA-Deteccion-de-superficies-regadas-y-estimacion-del-consumo-de-agua_AgriSat-UCLM-JCRMO.pdf</p>	AgriSat
<p>Garrido-Rubio, J., González-Piqueras, J., Campos, I., Osann, A., González Gómez, L., Calera Belmonte, A.,(2019). <i>Remote Sensing – based Soil Water Balance for irrigation water accounting at plot and water user association management scale for Agricultural Water Management</i>. Submission</p>	AgriSat

3.3. Participation and presentation at industry events

Further to scientific publications, a complementary way to achieve an effective dissemination is the participation of project partners in targeted non-project events. This covers a wide range of industry events, from technology-oriented to policy-oriented. The DIANA consortium partners have been active in several events in various modalities: oral or poster presentations, keynotes, panel members, exhibitors, and networking participants. Annex C provides a list of the

corresponding activities during the third year of the project. At the end of year 2 the participation in Events already exceed the initial target values.

3.4. DIANA stakeholder engagement events

The purpose of stakeholder engagement events is to interact with and mobilise regional and national stakeholder communities. The pilots form the nucleus of these events. Consequently, these stakeholder engagement events have been organized in Spain, in Romania, and in Italy. Some of these events have also been part of the continued co-creation process (WP1). Some of the events listed in Annex C (see section 3.2 above) have also served to enhance stakeholder engagement. Annex B provides the list of corresponding events that took place during the 3rd year, which at the end of year 2 already exceed the initial target values.

3.5. DIANA videos by partners

The production of promotional videos has been part of DIANA dissemination strategy from the beginning. In total, 13 DIANA videos have been produced (including a video presentation of the project, for dissemination after the end of the project). Video production has usually been carried out by project partners. During the first reporting period, 3 videos with users interviews were produced. They were uploaded on the DIANA YouTube channel. A guide for using DIANA platform is also available in our channel.

3.6. DIANA project video

One of the project goals was to ensure the dissemination of DIANA results after the end of the project. To this end, the concept for a general dissemination video was taken up. The video addresses both the public as well as target groups including policy makers, and focuses on the services delivered by DIANA project based on the EO data provided by Copernicus and other data sources. It is also argued that identification of (illegally) irrigated areas and the estimation of abstracted water volumes are the core DIANA services.

The video was finalised and published on the project website during the last week of November 2019. The video was also published on YouTube.

3.7. Mass media communication

Obtaining news coverage, whether at national or local level, increases the profile of the project to a great extent and enables the consortium to reach a very wide audience. The aim is to continue and utilize mass media communication activities to inform the general public about the DIANA project.

Error! Reference source not found. provides a list of the dissemination of the project through TV and radio channels, web media, and newspapers and magazines - either printed or electronic.

Table 5. Mass media communications

Article or Press release	Responsible Partner	Audience Size
<p>4 Feb 2019</p> <p>Diario de Sevilla</p> <p><i>Illegal risks, in the "Diana" of technology. Combating unauthorized watering and over-extraction of water.</i></p> <p>https://www.diariodesevilla.es/agr_andalucia/Riegos-ilegales-Diana-tecnologia_0_1324068101.html</p>	FERAGUA.	1/cabecera por provincia andaluza
<p>2 May 2019</p> <p>#EnRed. TV program where we explained DIANA project (in spanish). From 2.18 min</p> <p>#EnRed recorre las provincias de Huelva, Sevilla y Córdoba para conocer diferentes experiencias tecnológicas llamadas a controlar el riego eficiente en los cultivos. Desde sistemas que riegan cuando el terreno lo necesita hasta imágenes de satélite con las que comprobar el estado de los campos, Andalucía se está convirtiendo en un escenario pionero de estas apuestas por el ahorro del agua.</p> <p>https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=EGrAKaDvMXc&list=PLsHWVkJQOo4xE6-IYPyl0wXN40k2i5tgN&index=13&t=0s</p>	FERAGUA.	>15.000
<p>26 Mar 2019</p> <p>Senato TV</p>	Sannio Alifano	>350.000

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<p>9th Commission of the Senate of the Italian Republic (Agriculture and agri-food production) - Hearing of representatives of reclamation and irrigation consortia of Lombardy, Veneto, Emilia-Romagna, Campania and western Sicily</p>		
<p>29 Jun 2019 National Newspaper "La Repubblica". <i>La difesa dell'acqua per lo sviluppo locale. Presentation of Sannio Alifano projects to monitor crops development to define irrigation water requirements and optimize water consumption</i>. http://www.sannioalifano.it/images/file/2019/Articolo-quotidiano-Repubblica-29-06-2019.pdf</p>	<p>Sannio Alifano</p>	<p>With a circulation of 377.000</p>
<p>30 October 2019 National Newspaper: "La Repubblica Ed. Napoli" "<i>L'irrigazione per una agricoltura di qualità - Irrigation for quality agriculture</i>" regarding "Presentation of Sannio Alifano projects to monitor crops development and to provide irrigation advice to users". https://sannioalifano.it/images/file/2019/Articolo-quotidiano-Repubblica-30-10-2019.pdf</p>	<p>Sannio Alifano</p>	<p>With a circulation of 377.000</p>
<p>November 2019 AgroNews Castilla y León. <i>The DIANA Project: A platform of Detection of illegal water abstraction</i> https://www.agronewscastillayleon.com/el-proyecto-diana-una-plataforma-de-deteccion-de-usos-ilegales-de-agua-para-riego</p>	<p>FERAGUA</p>	<p>>1.500</p>
<p>November 2019. <i>La voz del Regadío. The DIANA Project: A platform of Detection of illegal water abstraction. Pilot area Bembezar</i> https://feragua.com/lavozdelregadio/2019/11/11/diana-reunion-en-roma-para-la-presentacion-de-la-plataforma-de-deteccion-de-usos-ilegales-de-agua-para-riego/</p>	<p>FERAGUA</p>	<p>With a circulation, 1.300 e-mails address to WUAs, farmers, public administrations</p>
<p>December 2019. <i>La voz del Regadío. River Basin Authority of Guadalquivir have an Interest of knowing DIANA H2020 project.</i> https://feragua.com/lavozdelregadio/2019/12/04/la-</p>	<p>FERAGUA</p>	<p>With a circulation, 1.300 e-mails</p>

confederacion-hidrografica-del-guadalquivir-se-interesa-por-diana/		address to WUAs, farmers, public administrations
December 2019 Eldiario.es El director general del Agua espera que la legislatura sea estable porque la política hidráulica no es “de corto plazo”. https://www.eldiario.es/politica/director-Agua-legislatura-politica-hidraulica_0_972903409.html	FERAGUA	National

3.8. Advisory Board

The Advisory Board is an integral part of DIANA project and its establishment assists the DIANA project to have access to valuable knowledge and expertise at all stages of the project implementation. Within that framework the Advisory Board also supports the project dissemination. Several Advisory Board members were present at important stakeholder engagement events.

3.9. Final Event

The DIANA Final Event was held on 11 December 2019 in Zaragoza, Spain, in the frame of the EIP-Water Innovation Conference (<https://www.eip-water.eu/eu-water-innovation-conference-2019-0>). A total of 27 attendants from 6 countries had registered (not counting the DIANA partners and Project Officer). The event was opened by the Water General Director of Spain (Ministry for the Ecological Transition), Manuel Menéndez. He also stressed the importance of DIANA solutions for water management and governance at several other events held during the same conference, as well as in national Newspaper interviews.

DIANA was also presented by the Director of GIS services in the Hydrological Planning Office of the Ebro River Basin Authority at another parallel event on the same day, organized by the “Partenariado el Agua en Aragón”, an operational group.

The merits of DIANA solutions were also highlighted at another parallel event assembling all Spanish River Basin Organizations, organized by the Ebro RBO and the Ministry for the Ecological Transition.

4. Conclusions and next steps

All planned dissemination and communication actions of the project have been carried out successfully and according to plan, some of them exceeding the initial target values. All consortium partners have taken part in the respective dissemination activities and contributed to achieving maximum attention and awareness beyond the project consortium.

All dissemination activities have been in line with the protection of IPR as well as the confidentiality obligations, which were established in the Consortium Agreement (CA). All partners have actively engaged in the dissemination and stakeholder engagement activities conducted so far and are committed to continue along the lifespan of the project and beyond.

The main assets disseminated have been: the DIANA data products and services; the DIANA service platform and its components including the web application; novel knowledge generated through the implementation of the project; and the data collected during the pilot implementation.

The target groups and audience for dissemination have been water managers, authorities, farmers, agricultural cooperatives and consultancies, research and academia, NGOs and civil society groups, other stakeholders, and the general public.

The dissemination and communication material and activities that have been produced or undertaken during the project include:

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- the visual identity of the project, established at the beginning of the project, aiming to set the baseline for a brand identity for the commercial service;
- a public website launched in M05 and regularly updated, to serve as a single source of information concerning the project results and activities, and to disseminate news;
- the DIANA page on Facebook, the LinkedIn group and the DIANA Twitter account, which provide platforms for communicating news and material related to DIANA to specific audiences (e.g. younger, technologically-aware farmers on Facebook), and for sharing the latest information on the DIANA services;
- the pilot area videos on DIANA YouTube channel;
- the general DIANA video for dissemination after the project.
- the project's newsletters, providing information, results and events related to the project;
- specific dissemination materials used and distributed at external conferences (i.e. audience-focused presentations);
- representation in conferences and media as well as the publication of scientific papers, enhancing DIANA's visibility and enabling the development of a solid network amongst agricultural and Earth Observation (EO) academic and industrial stakeholders at both European and regional level;
- the Final Event held in the context of the EIP-Water Innovation Conference in Zaragoza.

All dissemination and communication activities have been enhanced and amplified in the last project year. The intention has been to create success stories in different media, tailored to the different target audiences.

One of the project goal is to ensure the dissemination of DIANA results after the end of the project. To this end, the concept for a general dissemination video was taken up.

Annexes

Annex A. Scientific conference oral presentations

Table 6. Scientific conference Oral Presentations

Scientific conference oral presentation	Audience Size
28 January -01 February 2019 POLinSAR Conference Backscatter analysis using multi-temporal Sentinel 1 SAR data for irrigated crops monitoring in Banat region, Romania, poster presentation. Frascati, Italy .	
20-23 February 2019 FOSS4G-IT 2019. Software e Dati Geografici Free e Open Source FOSS4G-it 2019. Ariespace. Poster	
13-17 May 2019 ESA Living Planet Symposium, Assessment and monitoring of land degradation using Sentinel data in Banat Region, Romania, poster presentation. Milano,Italy	500
13-17 May 2019 ESA Living Planet Symposium, Milan, Italy Operation monitoring of irrigation in the Campania Region (Italy) for the compliance of EU Water Directive by using Sentinel-2 data: the DIANA Project	50
4-5 June 2019 The conference “Space for a Safe and Secure Society, supporting Sustainable Growth” took place in Bucharest.	
12 -13 September BIOSYSTEMS ENGINEERING FOR SUSTAINABLE AGRICULTURE, FORESTRY AND FOOD PRODUCTION. International Mid-Term Conference 2019 Italian Association of Agriculture Engineering (AIIA). Potenza/Matera, University of Basilicata	50

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Operational monitoring of Irrigation in the Campania Region (Italy) for the compliance of EU Water Directive by using Sentinel-2 data. ORAL PRESENTATION	
10 - 11 October International Workshop R³ in GEOMATICS: Research, Results And Review , Naples Italy Assessment of irrigated areas and irrigation abstraction for precise management of water - ORAL PRESENTATION	
12-14 November 2019 NATIONAL CONFERENCE. ASITA 2019 – Stazione marittima Trieste Operational monitoring of irrigation in Campania Region (Italy) using Harmonized Landsat Sentinel-2 product (HLS) ORAL PRESENTATION	

Annex B. Stakeholder engagement events and presentations

Table 7. Stakeholder engagement events and presentations

Event	Audience
<p>15 March 2019</p> <p>Training session CUAS Training session. Community of Underground Water Users Valdelobos. With Users from 29 local terms. (C.U.A.S). Albacete. Spain</p>	5
<p>28 March 2019</p> <p>Feragua General Meeting. The general meeting of Feragua takes place in Seville once per year. Most important items of the association are discussed and projects were Feragua is actively participating are presented. Managers from the WUAs and presidents are the audience.</p>	50
<p>12 April 2019</p> <p>Irrigation workshop</p> <p>Campania Region - Campania Land Reclamation Consortia. Napoli – Centro Direzionale Isola A/6. Consorzio di Bonifica Sannio Alifano</p> <p>https://www.sannioalifano.it/file2019/Presentazione_Workshop_mn_finale.pdf</p>	50
<p>6-10 May 2019</p> <p>DHI Romania and all the Water Basin Administrations delegates. Albota, Romania</p>	
<p>11-19 May 2019</p> <p>National week of reclamation and irrigation. Land Reclamation consortia leader in the development of the rural areas. <i>Special "info-point" for information on the next PAC (CAP - Common Agricultural Policy) and DIANA Project.</i></p>	
<p>28-29 May 2019</p> <p>Workshop Water and Agriculture - Water Abstraction.</p> <p>DIANA has been invited by the Task Force on Water and Agriculture of the Commission to make a presentation in the workshop titled "Water and Agriculture - Water</p>	100

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<p>Abstraction". The workshop took place on the 28th-29th of May 2019, in Madrid, Spain. (Anna Osann. AgriSat)</p>	
<p>12 June 2019</p> <p>Meeting at Ministry of Agriculture. Carlo de Michele (Ariespace) and Massimo Natalizio (Consorzio di Bonifica Del Sannio Alifano) attended a round table. The title of Massimo Natalizio speech was 'The European DIANA project: integration of satellite data into Consortium irrigation management'. Rome</p>	200
<p>17 June 2019</p> <p>Feragua presents the results of its participation in the DIANA and MOSES projects at the National Congress of Irrigation in Badajoz (Spain)</p> <p>Elena Navarro con una presentación denominada "Evaluación del uso del agua en el Sector BXII del Bajo Guadalquivir mediante el indicador del Suministro Relativo de Riego"</p> <p>https://feragua.com/lavozdelregadio/2019/06/17/feragua-presenta-en-el-congreso-nacional-de-regadio-en-badajoz-los-resultados-de-su-participacion-en-los-proyectos-moses-y-diana/</p>	150
<p>24-28 June 2019</p> <p>Water Basin Administrations and Technical University of Civil Engineering delegates. Magura, Romania</p> <p>https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/activities/un-romania.html</p>	
<p>9 October 2019</p> <p>"Presentation of Sannio Alifano activities" - Meeting with The Triveneta Association of Land Reclamation Consortia Managers of Veneto, Friuli-Venezia Giulia and Trentino-Alto Adige Regions (North Italy). Ing. Massimo Natalizio</p> <p>Piedimonte Matese (CE) 09/10/2019</p> <p>https://www.sannioalifano.it/file2019/Presentazione_Irrigazione_gen.pdf</p> <p>https://www.sannioalifano.it/file2019/Presentazione_Irrigazione_gestione.pdf</p>	50
<p>11-12 October 2019</p> <p>Copernicus and Space Applications Conference organized by ROSA and ESA. Bucharest</p>	
<p>17 October 2019</p> <p>Copernicus for Agri-environmental applications.</p>	150

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<p>1. Presentation of the results of the H2020 SENSAGRI project - Sentinels Synergy for Agriculture. Session 2. Copernicus for Water management (DIANA, FATIMA). Session 3: Copernicus for Climate Change: monitoring land use and land changes.</p> <p>Anna Osann. María Llanos López (AgriSat)</p> <p>https://eshorizonte2020.es/actualidad/eventos/copernicus-for-agri-environmental-applications</p>	
<p>17 and 18 October 2019</p> <p>Training Course - Remote sensing techniques for irrigation management at district (Consortium) scale; University of Salerno. <i>Ariespace</i> provide the technicians of Consortia, professionals and engineers, the fundamentals of remote sensing from satellite for better management of irrigation networks, assessment of irrigation volumes, identification of illegal irrigation, monitoring of territorial resources.</p>	40
<p>10-11 November 2019</p> <p>Fiera di San Martino 2019. Sannio Alifano Consortium participated with its own stand at the traditional San Martino Fair in the "Campagna Amica" exhibition spaces set up by Coldiretti. The Consortium has demonstrated, once again, also to non-experts, the importance and complexity of the organization and management of irrigation in agriculture.</p> <p>http://www.sannioalifano.it/26-news-home/497-anche-il-consorzio-di-bonifica-del-sannio-alifano-protagonista-alla-fiera-di-san-martino.html</p>	30
<p>19-20 November 2019</p> <p>Annual Scientific Conference of the National Institute of Hydrology and Water Management. Bucharest</p>	
<p>23 November 2019</p> <p>Workshop: “Gestión y buenas prácticas en material de utilización de agua, planificación de cultivos y optimización del recurso a través de la modernización de regadíos”. Water Users Asocition CUAS Rus-Valdelobos. San Clemente and Villarrobledo (Spain)</p> <p>https://www.dropbox.com/s/sblym3stxoy9u80/TRIPTICO%20SAN%20CLEMENTE-V4.pdf?dl=0</p>	50
<p>25-29 November 2019</p> <p>Water Basin Administrations and the Technical University of Civil Engineering delegates. Albota, Romania</p>	30

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<p>03 December 2019</p> <p>Workshop: “Gestión y buenas prácticas en material de utilización de agua, planificación de cultivos y optimización del recurso a través de la modernización de regadíos”. Water Users Asocition CUAS Rus-Valdelobos. San Clemente and Villarrobledo (Spain)</p> <p>https://www.dropbox.com/s/goueg1yuhvy5rv/TRIPTICO%20VILLARROBLEDO.pdf?dl=0</p>	<p>50</p>
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Annex C. Participation in events

Title of Event	Aim of the event	Participating Partner details	Audience characteristics	Audience Size
7-12 April 2019 EGU Conference Vienna	Detection of irrigated crops from Sentinel 1 and Sentinel 2 data to estimate seasonal water use. A case study: Banat pilot area, Romania , poster presentation Bucharest, Agriculture for Life, Life for Agriculture Conference, Analysis of the Sentinel 1 and Sentinel 2 data for mapping irrigated crops in the Big Island of Braila, oral presentation.	ROSA, NARW	Scientists, engineers, university educators	16.250 visitors
02-05 May 2019 Expovicaman XXXIX Agricultural and Livestock Fair of Castilla-La Mancha. Spain.	Expovicaman is the fair par excellence of the agricultural and livestock world with a long tradition and well rooted in Castilla-La Mancha region. Many exhibitors expose their products and latest advances for the agricultural world as well as the farmers show their best elements.	AgriSat Team	farmers, future users, technicians, politicians, manufacturer of Agricultural Machinery	>11.000 Visitors
06-10 May 2019 Conference on Space Solutions for Sustainable Agriculture and Precision Farming Cluj, Romania. United Nations/Romania International	The Conference is aiming to address key issues related to utilization of space technologies and solutions for a sustainable agriculture, addressing number of indicators and targets under the sustainable Development Goals framework and considering the challenges related to food security worldwide, with increasing populations	ROSA	Scientists, engineers, university educators, policy-and-decision makers, senior experts	600

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	and corresponding pressures on the available agricultural land.			
13-17 May 2019, European Space Agency's 2019 Living Planet Symposium. Milan, Italy.	This symposium focuses on how Earth Observation contributes to science and society, and how disruptive technologies and actors are changing the traditional Earth Observation landscape, which is also creating new opportunities for public and private sector interactions.	ROSA. Ariespace.	Scientifics, public and private experts, local and national audience, EO data analysis and applications technicians	800
8-10 July 2019 ECPA 2019	Focus on precision farming applied to small Mediterranean farms. Montpellier https://ecpa2019.agrotic.org/	AgriSat	International event	380 attendees from 34 countries
13-14 Sept 2019 VII Edizione a Piedimonte Matese (CE) Festival dell'Erranza.	Words and Water. The theme of 2019 edition is "Words and water" The event hosted a series of meetings with experts and managers in the field of water resources. Historical photographic exhibition "Hydraulic reclamation, irrigation systems and networks: together with Italy for 150 years", presented on display by the CREA, and for the presentation of the European project H 2020 DIANA "Irrigation with satellites", by the Consorzio di Bonifica del Sannio Alifano. http://www.festivaldellerranza.it/	Consorzio di Bonifica Sannio Alifano. AgriSat. Anna Osann	Experts and managers in the field of water resources, journalists, writers, religious, entrepreneurs and artists to question the preciousness of water and words and their similarities	600

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<p>18 September 2019</p> <p>Workshop 'THE FUTURE OF THE CEREAL IN CASTILLA Y LEÓN'</p>	<p>AgriSat was in charge of "dosis variable para parcelas variables: la teledetección al servicio del agricultor"</p> <p>https://laagriculturadigital.com/feria-virtual/vi-congreso-el-futuro-del-cereal-en-castilla-y-leon/</p>	<p>AgriSat. Sponsor</p>	<p>farmers, machinery manufacturers, governmental bodies, and service providers</p>	<p>200</p>
<p>1 October 2019</p> <p>VIII Annual Day AWA Canal del Pisuerga. Ávila, Spain</p>	<p>Looking for alternative crops for modernization of irrigation systems</p>	<p>AgriSat</p>	<p>AWAs, farmers, machinery manufacturers, governmental bodies, and service providers</p>	<p>50</p>
<p>8 October 2019</p> <p>Workshop on EO downstream services in Horizon Europe -, Brussels</p>	<p>The main objective of the workshop will be to gather feedback and recommendations from the H2020 EO downstream projects to feed into the wider stakeholder consultation process led by DG GROW for the preparation of the Horizon Europe space programme.</p> <p>http://www.cdti.es/recursos/eventosCDTI/35864_3103_10201983025.pdf</p>	<p>Agroapps. AgriSat</p>	<p>European H2020 beneficiaries, DG of EC. National representatives from the Copernicus User Forum.</p>	<p>400</p>
<p>4 November 2019</p> <p>Workshop – CREA – Rome</p> <p>Innovative technologies for management and monitoring of water and nutrients in agricultural area.</p>	<p>The aim of the study day is to bring to the attention of managers, technicians and professionals dealing with the management of water resources in agriculture (managers and technicians of reclamation consortia, Regions and the Ministry) the most recent research results to improve monitoring and the management of irrigation networks and other agronomic inputs.</p>	<p>Organization Ariespace SRL, Host Partner CREA-AA.</p>	<p>DIANA partners, MIPAAF, Technicians, professionals and engineers</p>	<p>100</p>
<p>12-16 Nov 2019</p> <p>AgriTechnica</p>	<p>The world's leading trade fair for agricultural technology, organized by</p>	<p>AgriSat</p>	<p>investors, farmers,</p>	<p>2.820 exhibitors</p>

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2019. Hannover	DLG, all the leading companies in the industry present their innovations. https://www.agritechnica.com/en/		buyers, technology manufacturers, machinery manufacturers, governmental bodies, and service providers	& 450.000 visitors
3-4 Dec 2019 Women in Food & Agriculture, Amsterdam	The world's leading agribusiness and food companies at this exciting global summit launch dedicated to inclusion and diversity. Celebrate the achievements of those who are the backbone of the world's food systems. https://www.wfasummit.com/	AgriSat. Lead Partner	The prominent players of the agri industry. Different sectors of the Agriculture.	300
11-12 Dec 2019 Final Event & Congress 11/12/19: Final Event DIANA 12/12/19: EIP Water Innovation Congress	https://www.eip-water.eu/eu-water-innovation-conference-2019-0 https://www.eip-water.eu/side-meetings-eip-water-conference-2019	All partners/Agri Sat	DIANA partners, EC. Representatives, scientifics, Technicians, professionals	700

Table 8. Participation of consortium in events

Annex D. List of videos

Video Title / Partner	Link to the video
DIANA video. Sannio Alifano.	https://diana-h2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/video-sannio-diana-1.mp4? =1

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Guide for using DIANA platform	https://youtu.be/5duocejr9JY
Convegno Festival dell Erranza Piedimonte Matese	https://youtu.be/pWMMQc3fh3to
Video from #enred TVprogram, where FERAGUA explained DIANA project (in spanish).	https://youtu.be/LqJUbfzwCKc
DIANA Feragua. Pilot zone Bembezar SP. Interview with Jose Luis Murcia, manager WUA	https://youtu.be/_S0luphkQ8M
DIANA Inverview with Massimo Natalizio. Italian	https://youtu.be/UZo1ZGuJSRU
Irrisat Stories. DIANA interview with Camilo MASTRACCHIO. Italian	https://youtu.be/7kDyoQV3NSM
IRRISAT STORIES. DIANA interview with Luca GIORDANO. Italian	https://youtu.be/xuFyuMUbmfs
DIANA interview with NARWans ISPIF english embedded subs	https://youtu.be/24uOcEMGneA
DIANA interview with NARWans ISPIF (english optional subs)	https://youtu.be/Lx82zJLwMPU
DIANA interview with JCRMO Technical Director (English subtitles)	https://youtu.be/LlewJ0SHNg4
DIANA entrevista con el Director Técnico de la JCRMO	https://youtu.be/H09KBzDCE8c

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(Spanish)	
TV report on Italian pilot area and stakeholder event. Owned by MEDIA TV	https://youtu.be/akLODI4byU

Table 9. List of project videos

